

The role of the Virtual Test Bed in ensuring perennial and reproducible computational nuclear engineering research

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ABSTRACT

For a variety of reasons, computational nuclear engineering studies may be, or rapidly become, irreproducible after their publication. This could arise for a variety of reasons, from unavailable export controlled software, to insufficient version control in the inputs and the codes. In the Virtual Test Bed (hosted at https://github.com/idaholab/virtual_test_bed), a library of reference advanced reactor multiphysics models using modern nuclear simulation software, the rigorous continuous integration program we have lead over the past five years has handled considerable changes in the software and the simulations hosted. This ensures that simulation results remain updated and reproducible.

Keywords: VTB, NEAMS, Research Reproducibility, Publications

1. INTRODUCTION

Computational tools are widely used in nuclear engineering for design, licensing and operation. They help characterize the behavior of the numerous physics at play in nuclear reactors, usually neutron transport, thermal-hydraulics, fuel behavior, and structural mechanics. Codes such as Monte Carlo codes [1, 2] and finite element/volume-based frameworks [3, 4] are widely used for research purposes but present additional challenges for reproducibility. These specific tools enable high-fidelity simulations that are essential for reactor design, safety analysis, and licensing. However, the complexity of these simulations makes them difficult to reproduce without significant effort from the initial researchers.

In this paper, we will first describe the Virtual Test Bed (VTB) [5] and the process of publishing models on the VTB, and then we will cover sources of irreproducibility in computation research, followed by best practices that can alleviate the issue. These best practices will be examined in the context of the Virtual Test Bed.

2. PUBLISHING MODELS ON THE VIRTUAL TEST BED

The Virtual Test Bed was founded in 2020 within the National Reactor Innovation Center. It is an online, open-source, repository of advanced reactor modeling and simulation cases that is actively maintained and co-developed with the Nuclear Energy Advanced Modeling and Simulation (NEAMS) software. The repositories holds 71 models of sodium fast reactors, molten salt reactors, pebble bed reactors, micro-reactors, research reactors and fusion devices. As the capabilities of this software grow with this research and development program's efforts, the Virtual Test Bed is expanded to host validation, verification, and demonstration cases. These cases are often enabled by the high fidelity capabilities offered

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by the NEAMS tools. Several of the NEAMS codes are themselves open-source, while the rest are export-controlled with various degrees of restrictions according to the U.S. code of federal regulations.

Contributions to the Virtual Test Bed may be performed by all via pull requests to the repository on GitHub. Maintenance and integration of the models is currently set up with twelve codes that are all developed by the NEAMS program. Griffin for neutronics, Grizzly for structural mechanics, Bison for fuel performance, SAM for systems analysis, RELAP-7 for compressible flow systems analysis, Pronghorn and NekRS for computational fluid dynamics, Cardinal, DireWolf and BlueCrab for multiphysics. Many of these codes leverage the Multiphysics Object Oriented Simulation Environment (MOOSE) [6] to represent and solve equations on an unstructured mesh.

Each model on the VTB must include the model input files, the data to run these inputs (e.g., a meshed geometry), the reference results and tests specifications, and extensive documentation of the inputs and the model results. The testing is often set up by the VTB team to simplify the contribution. The documentation is generally extracted from a previous publication, which is often a technical report over a journal article due to the level of details required to explain an input file.

Once contributed, the model is actively tested on every change in the software. In case the results of the models change, the differences are investigated by the VTB team in collaboration with the software developers and often the original contributors of the model. The reference results are generally updated, as the software should only ever be improved.

3. CHALLENGES FOR REPRODUCIBILITY

Achieving reproducibility in modeling and simulation research is not trivial. In this section, we will list numerous challenges, greatly alleviated by the practices outlined in Section 4.

3.1. Simulation Results Evolving over Time and Insufficient Version Information

Most of the NEAMS tools follow continuous integration and continuous improvement practices. As the codes are updated, the solutions to the simulations change. Unless the exact version of the code used for the publication is used, there is no guarantee that the input for the model will produce the same results.

Similarly, the inputs evolve. While a frozen version is used for publication, inputs are typically re-used to create further iterations of the models, which may not be published. Even if procuring the inputs from the publication authors, unless the version of the inputs is tracked rigorously, there is a chance the inputs do not reproduce the publication results.

The version of the software can be tracked its major/minor version, for example MCNP 6.3.0, or by its current commit hash. The commit hash is a unique identifier for the state of the code. It is an alphanumeric string precisely identifies that specific set of changes, and can be retrieved and examined from the repository.

To this day, it is relatively rare in nuclear engineering publications to have the commit hash (=version) for the exact version of the software used, except for select versioned tools such as MCNP. It is even rarer to have the versions of the input files, or the input files themselves, available with the publication. Compounded with the changes previously mentioned, this makes the results from these publications hard to reproduce.

3.2. Variability and Stochasticity from Numerical Schemes

Computational research can be difficult to reproduce for numerical reasons. The results of finite element simulations can greatly depend on the mesh used, notably if there are problematic elements causing convergence issues. Even in simulations with no such defects, the solver configuration, such as the

Figure 1. The VTB CI/CD workflow for simulation models. In the Dev phase (local development), a researcher creates a model and opens an issue, then works on a new branch with local testing and validation. After that, a Pull Request (PR) is submitted, triggering CI (Continuous Integration) where automated tests run. If all tests pass, the code undergoes peer review. Upon approval, the changes are merged into the main branch. In the deployment phase, the model and documentation are published, and the model becomes available for reuse and maintenance. Future updates begin by opening a new issue, linking back to the development phase, thus iterating the cycle.

selection of the preconditioner or the effect of the partitioning on the preconditioner can also greatly influence results.

In MOOSE, we execute the test suite using from 1 to 16 processes to ensure that the test suite is resilient to differences in preconditioning. The effect of block preconditioning is different based on the partitioning, and the default preconditioners are different in serial and parallel. In the Virtual Test Bed, we have not implemented such testing. The reference results are generated then tested with different numbers of cores, which replicates some of this effect.

3.3. Sensitivity of Results to Modeling Parameters

In the case that the exact input is not shared, a model that would greatly depend on the simulation parameters, for example numerical settings or the mesh, would be difficult to reproduce.

3.4. Sensitivity of results to computing architecture

For models that are sensitive to the numerical methods used, the computing architecture is likely to matter as well: the numerical methods can be implemented differently to run optimally on a CPU or a GPU for example. As previously mentioned, the number of processes, often tied to the number of cores on the CPU, may matter as well for the numerical solve.

3.5. Insufficient description in publication

Another likely common causes for difficulties in reproducing computational research is the insufficient description of the system in a publication. In general, complex systems include many geometry/mesh/materials details that are not provided for the sake of conciseness. Additionally, proprietary design parameters may be excluded deliberately. In the Virtual Test Bed, we host input files directly, and thus naturally provide a sufficient description of the system.

3.6. Reproducibility Issues from Data-based Machine-learning Modeling Methods

Numerous data-based methods use stochastic treatments such as stochastic drop-out layers or stochastic gradient descent techniques when training a neural network. As a result, providing the data openly is insufficient to reproduce the neural network. Instead, the trained network in its entirety should be provided, either in the form of open weights or directly. This requires open code repositories, as previously mentioned.

The Virtual Test Bed currently hosts a pebble bed reactor simulation which uses a trained reduced order model [7]. The reduced order model is generated in the inputs provided, in a deterministic manner, thus these concerns have not materialized.

3.7. Human and Institutional Factors

Reproducibility is hard to measure and is generally not a metric in proposal or personnel performance evaluations. As such, it is not a priority for most researchers, and the efforts to mitigate the previously mentioned problems are more likely to arise from researchers' professional ethic than from an institutional effort. The pressure to publish novel results, combined with limited incentives for performing replication or verification studies, can further contribute to irreproducibility.

4. BEST PRACTICES FOR REPRODUCIBLE RESEARCH

Avoiding these pitfalls for reproducibility is not impossible, and following best practices greatly simplifies the process. The Virtual Test Bed is a key part of following these practices within the programs that contribute models.

4.1. Open Science Practices

The most important step for reproducible science is sharing information. Providing input files, post-processing scripts and source data is key to enabling others to reproduce the results. In computational nuclear engineering, it is often the case that the software is not available openly; for example MCNP [2] is export-controlled and is not available publicly. However, it is also often the case that an alternate, open-source software can reproduce study results within reason; for example OpenMC [1] can be used to reproduce most studies with MCNP. This possibility generally depends on how physical models and numerics compare in these codes.

In the Virtual Test Bed, we provide all input files, meshes, and data to run the models on the repository. For models involving export-controlled codes, we cannot provide the software to run them; users must obtain a license independently from the NCRC [8]. However, for models that run with open-source codes, git submodules are available within the Virtual Test Bed for each open-source code, which is notably used for continuous integration. Save for rare exceptions during maintenance situations, these inputs will run with the corresponding version of the submodule and produce the desired results.

Beyond sharing inputs and data, open-science practitioners also use containerization to preserve the exact version of the binaries used to produce the results. Containerization is the process of packaging software applications with all their dependencies, libraries, and configuration files into a single, portable "container". This allows the application to run consistently and reliably across different computing environments by isolating it from the underlying infrastructure while sharing the host operating system's kernel. In the Virtual Test Bed, and on INL's computing clusters, we use containers to deploy the software for running the test suite; however, note that these containers are saved only for a limited time, roughly a couple of months. Note that this does not impede reproducibility, as the scripts to build the containers are version-controlled, and can be re-run in the future to reproduce the containers.

4.2. Internal Peer Review and Quality Assurance Programs

At Idaho National Laboratory, in the Nuclear Science and Technology directorate, every publication, article, presentation or technical report, undergoes an internal peer review step before submission for release. This additional peer review step is part of the rigorous quality assurance program that the directorate follows. Similarly, every code contribution for the various software developed by the NEAMS program are reviewed by one or two independent reviewers.

The Virtual Test Bed adds an additional layer of peer review to the process. The documentation of each model is checked for accessibility and completeness. The inputs are cleared of all deprecation and checked while building the test suite. The results are updated in collaboration with the contributor. Larger cases must produce consistent results across a variety of architectures. However, this process is not a requirement of the quality assurance program for NEAMS or NRIC.

4.3. Software Development Practices

Continuous integration is a key part in achieving lasting reproducible research. For every change in the code, the cases of interest are solved again by the test suite and an error is produced if the results have changed. While the results for a given case may change, the change is reflected in the version control system of the case. If the previous results are desirable for the sake of reproducibility, it is known which version of the code and the inputs can be used to produce them.

In the Virtual Test Bed, we adopt a multi-layered approach to continuous integration to both limit the cost of testing and ensure a sustainable path forward while complex breakage is addressed. The approach relies on running tests in two different manners: when updating an application, and when changing the version of the application submodule in the Virtual Test Bed.

When modifying an application, the Virtual Test Bed syntax and regression test suite for the cases solved with that given application is run. Additional tests, usually involving a regression test of the full scale model, may be run using a high performance computing cluster. Due to their computational cost, these tests are only run when the version of the application submodules on the Virtual Test Bed is changed.

4.4. Utilizing Known Benchmark Problems

Using community benchmarks can improve reproducibility. Benchmarks are familiar to a larger group of researchers who can easily compare and/or reproduce results on a case they are familiar with. Peer reviewers are more likely to be familiar with the level of error that are acceptable on a known benchmark. For example, the C5G7 benchmark [9], the BEAVRS benchmark [10] and VERA suite of benchmarks [11] are well-known to light water reactor physics researchers, and numerous methods were demonstrated on these benchmarks [12, 13, 14, 15].

The Virtual Test Bed hosts solutions to numerous benchmarks, such as the CNRS [16], the IAEA VP-1, and the VP-3 [17] benchmarks. The hosted solutions can be reproduced at any time by a user with access to the employed codes. Several benchmarks can be solved using only open-source software.

4.5. Education and Training

Best practices in computational research are best taught early. Version control is a useful skill for class projects in computational methods, as are collaborative coding practices and standardized development methods. Additionally, ethics in research classes can emphasize the importance of reproducibility and following best practices. In curricula without such classes, workshops, seminars, and tutorials can act as substitutes. As most, if not all, universities in the United States with a nuclear engineering department also have a computer science/engineering (CS) department, it is realistic for a class on software practices, from the CS department, to be included in computational nuclear research tracks.

4.6. Funding and Journal Policies

The existence of guidelines is of little use if they are not followed. Since research institutions around the world care about funding and publications, an actionable way to impose improvements would be for funding agencies and journals to require their adoption. Proposals could be mandated to include a plan for producing open science, and journals could require the publication of code, model and/or data, within the limits of applicable law. Similar to the relatively recent deployment of contribution statements in many major publications, the journals could impose the inclusion of a “how to reproduce” section. This section would be fairly trivial for research groups using a repository such as the Virtual Test Bed, and more involved when the tools, methodology and inputs are unavailable or unpublished.

Additionally, regularly or systematically supporting replication studies would naturally verify the reproducibility of research. Independent replication studies can root out mistakes in the initial studies, and increase confidence in the results. A path to publication could be facilitated for such studies, to increase their appeal for researchers who otherwise reap more benefits from novel research.

5. CONCLUSIONS

While there are numerous challenges to overcome to produce reproducible computational nuclear studies, it is fundamental for the credibility and progress of nuclear reactor physics that much efforts be made in that direction. The challenges can be overcome with the best practices we have laid out in this paper. The Virtual Test Bed, and a larger corpus of sustainable software development, deployment, and management practices, is key to ensuring lasting and reproducible computational studies.

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